

THE STRUCTURE OF SOCIAL AND HUMANITARIAN WORK IN MODERN UNIVERSITY: THEORETICAL ASPECT

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Abstract

The article examines the socio-humanitarian work of higher education as a specific activity deliberately aimed at preparing the younger generation for life in accordance with the economic, political, moral, aesthetic and other goals of society, has significant potential in the process of forming cultural values of future primary school teachers, taking into account such directions: civil-patriotic, professional-labor, spiritual-moral, cultural-mass. The article is aimed at increasing the understanding of the role of values in the educational process and their influence on the social and humanitarian activities of students, with the purpose of training graduates ready for productive activities in modern society.

Keywords: social and humanitarian work, values, institution of higher education, directions of education.

Higher education is a main element of the social and cultural development of any society. It not only prepares a new generation of specialists, but promotes the development of citizenship, democracy, human rights and other social and humanitarian values. There are features of the modern world: globalization, technological changes, socio-economic and political challenges. It means that higher education constantly needs to review its approaches and strategies, especially when it is carried out under martial law.

Social and humanitarian work at the university is becoming more and more important, since the majority of students and teachers are at the epicenter of social challenges. Education isn't limited to academic knowledge, but also includes the development of citizenship, ethics, and critical thinking.

Social and humanitarian work in universities plays a critically important role in the personal development of students and the formation of an active civic position in them.

L. Baikova, O. Bozhko, L. Belova, O. Bylyk, A. Grechanyk, O. Dubaseniuk, O. Durmanenko, L. Zueva, A. Kondratyuk, D. Pashchenko, S. Polyakova, G. Trotsko, N. Udovenko, M. Fitsula. Modern scientists focus attention on the fact that a significant potential in the process of forming a personality and its value system at the student stage lies precisely in the social and humanitarian work of a higher educational institution: S. Bader, M. Konoh, Yu. Lukyanenko, A. Kharchenko, A. Chernenko, V. Yurchenko.

Based on the scientific studies of M. Fitsula, V. Bespalko, and M. Chebotko, we distinguish the following structural components of social and humanitarian work at universities: goal, subjects, content, forms and methods, result [1].

The *general goal* of the university's social and humanitarian work should correspond to the social order of society, be focused not only on the quality professional training of future teachers, but also on the formation of spiritual and moral principles, value orientations, and cultural values. It is obvious that the goal of

the university's social and humanitarian work is the ideally presented result of such work, the modeling of which depends both on the social order of society and on the traditions of the higher educational institution.

Society and the state in one way or another project their educational goal – the education of comprehensively developed personality, which is characterized by morality, patriotism, independence, entrepreneurship and the ability to intercultural communication [2]. That is, the state strives to get such a person who will be able to work for the benefit of society in the future, and this is natural, since the majority of educational institutions are financed from budget funds, which means that they have grounds to demand from the student the formation of the necessary qualities.

On the other hand, personality is a unique phenomenon, since it has a set of unique values (value-sense paradigm – S. Bader [3]), needs, qualities, and a single educational model will not work one way or another, we can only talk about an average educational result. I. Bech in his works claims that educational work cannot pursue the direct achievement of the goal, since this is impossible from the point of view of the uniqueness of the person, as well as from the point of view of the time frame [4].

As part of our research, we also highlight the student's personal goal in social and humanitarian work in the higher education system. It is a reflection of the meaning of a person's life, his personal aspirations, interests and desires, where he can find a point of support for self-development and self-improvement, taking into account the cultural values of society as a whole. That is why the most important task of social and humanitarian work is the formation of cultural values of future specialists, which will become the basis of their spiritual choice.

The *subjects* of the university's social and humanitarian work include: representatives of the rector's office, the teaching staff of the departments, including advisors, and, of course, the students themselves. However, it should be borne in mind that the rejection of the formal model in the educational work of the university

will be possible only in the case of subject-subject interrelation between all participants of the educational process. This is due to the fact that the formation of values, including cultural ones, is impossible by their direct imposition, when the teacher a priori positions himself above the student. In this case, values imposed from the outside are rejected, and their interiorization is possible only with the active inclusion of students in active activities with a positive emotional mode [5].

Subject-subject interaction presupposes the activity and initiative of the student himself, his subjective position, independence, responsibility for his choice during the implementation of the set goals. Unfortunately, teachers are often simply not ready for such interaction, being trapped by old stereotypes, when values are simply translated as generally accepted, important dogmas, and the educational process is based on the model of knowledge transmission as an axiom.

That is why subject-subject interaction is an extremely important condition for the formation of cultural values of future teachers.

In addition, in the process of social and humanitarian work, relationships in the «teacher – student» system acquire a more informal character, especially when it comes to mass cultural and volunteer activities, which facilitates the process of forming student's cultural values.

The *content* of social and humanitarian work in a university is one of the most controversial issues in modern pedagogical science. On the one hand, it is important to consider such areas as moral, physical, labor education; secondly, it is extremely important to carry out social and humanitarian activities in accordance with the real needs and interests of students, because it is then that the formation of cultural values of future teachers will become possible.

Let's dwell on the directions of social and humanitarian work of the university in the context of the formation of cultural values of future of primary school teachers. In the scientific literature, the following directions of social and humanitarian work of the university are distinguished: professional (professionally oriented), cultural (cultural-moral, cultural-mass), spiritual (moral), patriotic, civil (civil-legal), physical and recreational (sports) [5].

We will characterize each direction from the point of view of the formation of cultural values of future primary school teachers. Thus, one of the most significant is the civil-patriotic direction, since we attribute citizenship and patriotism to the leading cultural values of future teachers.

In the reference literature, a fairly comprehensive definition of the purpose of civic education is given: «education in a person of the moral ideals of society, feelings of love for the Motherland, the desire for peace, the need to work for the benefit of society» [6]. The consciousness of a person who responsibly fulfills his civic duty and understands that not only his own life depends on his actions, but also the fate of the closest people, the nation and the state, determines his social behavior and is an essential condition for the development of society.

As we can see, the cultural values that are important to form in future teachers are laid down in the goals of this social and humanitarian direction, since they will be the translators of these values for the younger generation.

The main direction of civic and patriotic education should be education based on the military and labor traditions of the people [7]. This will make it possible to form respect for the history, traditions and cultural values of the country, to cultivate hard work.

In the process of the university's social and humanitarian activities, it is important to integrate such forms and methods of work into civic and patriotic education: mass events, exhibitions, festivals dedicated to memorable dates, competitions, excursions to places of military glory, curatorial activities (curator's hours dedicated to the history of Ukraine, biographies outstanding heroes).

Thus, civic-patriotic education contributes to the formation of such cultural values of future primary school teachers as: citizenship, patriotism, responsibility, social activity.

In turn, vocational training at the university is aimed at establishing and strengthening the humanistic foundations of the future primary school teacher, his civic responsibility, the development of social activity, sociability and creative ambition.

Undoubtedly, this direction of the university's systemic social and humanitarian work is directed, first of all, to the future profession, but the cultural values of the future primary school teacher can't be separated from it, and hard work, as a native Ukrainian value, is successfully formed in various types of social and humanitarian work.

In the process of vocational education, the student has the opportunity to engage in volunteer activities, socially useful work, which forms such qualities and values as responsibility, mercy, humanity, hard work.

Spiritual and moral education of future primary school teachers is one of the most important tasks of higher education institutions, as it consists not in separately conducted educational and curatorial times, but in creating a spiritual and values atmosphere in the educational institution, which will contribute to the formation of the entire spectrum of values, awakening the desire in individuals show moral feelings reflected in moral behavior.

Spiritual and moral education at the university contributes to:

- formation and development of a system of spiritual and moral knowledge and values, realization of knowledge related to norms of morality and professional ethics;

- formation of students' cultural awareness and attitudes to the observance of cultural traditions and customs (including the creation of a family as the basis of the revival of traditional national moral values);

- *the formation of leadership qualities of a person who has the skills of self-presentation, argumentation, decision-making, organization of socially useful and personally significant affairs* [8].

The cultural and mass direction of the educational work of the university is designed to form the cultural

values of the future primary school teacher through the mechanisms of identification and emotional inclusion.

Cultural and mass events at the university are a special type of social and humanitarian work, which, thanks to its content, the use of means and methods of emotional impact on students, covers the spiritual life of the widest possible range of subjects with the goal of their comprehensive spiritual development.

Attending mass cultural events, the student identifies himself with a specific group, receives positive emotions and perceives positively colored information through the visual and auditory channels.

L. Kondrashova believes that the cultural and mass direction in social and humanitarian work is the most popular among young people, and based on the level and forms of conducting such events, it is possible to draw conclusions about the degree of cultural development in society. In addition, scientists emphasize that the meaningful content of the cultural and mass direction of educational work makes it possible to ascertain current trends in culture [9].

As we see, the mass cultural direction reflects the tendencies of society and the cultural values it professes. On the other hand, in an easy, emotionally attractive form, it can influence the students' consciousness and accelerate the process of accepting important values.

The *forms and methods* of social and humanitarian work at the university should also resonate with the interests and existing values of future primary school teachers.

For the formation of cultural values of future primary school teachers, it is extremely important to competently combine the forms and methods of work to implement each of the tasks, taking into account the needs of students and the level of values already formed in them.

The *result* of the social and humanitarian work of the university is extremely difficult to measure, since it is determined by the so-called «education of the future specialist», which is also a multifaceted category. In addition, in pedagogical science, it is difficult to apply strict criteria for measuring education levels. We consider the measurement of the effectiveness of the educational activity of the university by the number of conducted activities followed by the compilation of reports on achievements to be one of the outdated phenomena. As a result, formal work takes place, which does not concern changes in the structure of the student's personality.

Effective educational work can be considered if there are qualitative changes in the student's personality, his establishment as a citizen, the formation of his personal, professional and cultural values [10].

As we can see, the analysis of the structure of the social and humanitarian work of the university makes it possible to consider it as an effective means of forming the cultural values of students, since this task is already aimed at correlating with the social demand of society. Of course, it largely depends on the system of interrelationships between subjects, content, forms and

methods of educational activity, which must meet the needs of a modern student.

Thus, the special role of social and humanitarian work consists in the fact that it is aimed at expanding the cultural and social horizons of students, ensuring their preparation not only for professional activities, but also for life in the complex social conditions of the modern world. The social and humanitarian work of the university is one of the mechanisms of forming the intellectual, social and cultural potential of the nation.

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